

A proposal for improving the Epidemiological Surveillance System focused on infectious diseases at the Workplace.

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Summary

Introduction: Epidemiological Surveillance Systems (ESS) collect and analyze data to guide public health decisions, which is essential in pandemics such as the H1N1 flu and COVID-19. In Colombia, there is little information on ESS in work environments, and the absenteeism is not used to detect infectious disease. This project adapts guidelines from the Colombian Ministry of Health to create an ESS focused on communicable diseases in workers at the university. **Objective:** To design an Epidemiological Surveillance System (ESS) for infectious diseases in workers at the university, integrating new variables into the database and facilitating access to information in real-time. This allows timely notification to the corresponding entities and to characterize the working population with a higher frequency of infectious diseases. **Methods:** A systematic search conducted in databases about surveillance systems in workers, identifying areas for improvement in the University's ESS, particularly in monitoring based on absenteeism. Then we performed a secondary database analysis of 11,691 registers of absenteeism in a period between 2015 and 2024. **Results:** 28% of work incapacity was due to infectious diseases. **Conclusions:** The proposal for early detection and rapid response to disease infection represents a step towards a safer work environment and improving case management. However, its success also depends on protocols that ensure data privacy and maintain worker confidentiality. This system allows effective occupational health policies to address absenteeism issues.

Keywords

Epidemiological surveillance system, epidemiological surveillance system, workers, employees

Introduction

Epidemiological Surveillance Systems (ESS) are a continuous process of collecting, analyzing and interpreting health data, designed to support decision-making and guide public health interventions. These systems allow those responsible to evaluate the health situation and the impact of the actions implemented, guaranteeing timely and evidence-based responses for the prevention and control of diseases and injuries in the population.⁽¹⁻³⁾, ESS became more important during epidemics and pandemics such as pandemic influenza A (H1N1v), Human Immunodeficiency Virus, Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Virus and the COVID-19 pandemic.⁽⁴⁾.

Information on ESS of infectious diseases in the work environment in Colombia is scarce,(5)Absenteeism has been used as the primary early detection method for infectious outbreaks(6.7)but not for occupational exposure to possible infectious agents(8)However, a qualitative study entitled “Intervention strategies for the health of nursing workers in university hospitals in Brazil” conducted in 2013 showed a prevalence of physiological loads of 36.8%, biological loads of 27.2%, mechanical loads of 25.9% and psychic loads of 18.9% in exposed workers, and it was also observed that the physical demands faced by workers were related to biological risks, because they often arise from accidents with biological materials.(9)

In the university work context, the scientific basis for the development of the SVE for workers at a university was developed based on the Ministry of Health document “Guide for workers exposed to biological risk” which focuses on biological risk accidents, not on infectious diseases (10)

The justification of the project is based on the systematic search of scientific literature, since there is a lot of information about biological risk in workers, especially focused on times of pandemic and post-pandemic, however, there is not much emphasis on common infectious diseases related to specific work areas and the implementation of a respective follow-up and early warning.

General objective

Design ESS of biological risk related to infectious diseases in workers.

Specific objectives

- To characterize the main infectious diseases related with absenteeism.
- Propose new variables for the existing database for monitoring cases of infectious diseases

Methods

A structured literature search conducted in databases such as Pubmed, Scielo, Scopus and Embase. A search strategy defined that included the selection of relevant descriptors, ensuring their correspondence between the DeCS and MeSH terms relevant to our area of interest. The following keywords were established: “epidemiological surveillance system OR epidemiologic surveillance system” “workers OR employees”, focusing on infectious diseases in workers. It found that the available data are oriented to health workers and accidents due to biological risk. By analyzing the Epidemiological Surveillance document of workers at university, aspects to improve in its system identified, which uses work absenteeism reporting as a basis for detecting potential risks.

A secondary analysis of database focus in infection diseases; included a descriptive statistical analysis made of the absenteeism records contained in the institutional database for the period 2015-2024, highlighting both the affected positions and the accumulated days of absenteeism.

Results

The secondary analysis of the absenteeism database reviewed 11,691 registers with at least one episode of absenteeism in the period 2015-2024 analyzed. The distribution by sex showed 8,176 women and 3,515 men, representing 70% and 30% of absences, respectively. The main cause of absenteeism is general illness greater than 3 days with a total of 65,036 days, work accidents 3,760 days, isolation certificates 1,233 days.

In a sample of 2,985 workers, various infectious diseases identified as 28% of work-related sick days off, selecting only those with a prevalence equal to or greater than 1%.

Upper respiratory infections were the main cause of absenteeism, with the following pathologies standing out: acute rhinopharyngitis (common cold) with 1,158 cases, followed by acute bronchitis with 170 cases, acute laryngitis with 150 cases, acute pharyngitis with 147 cases, acute tonsillitis with 136 cases, and acute pharyngitis caused by other viruses with 67 cases. Gastroenteritis with 858 cases is the second most common cause of absenteeism, followed closely by COVID-19 from an identified virus with a report of 517 cases. These data highlight the importance of preventing and managing respiratory infections in the workplace (see figure 1).

Figure 1: Most common infectious-contagious pathologies at workplace

Discussion

The review of the literature and the databases evaluated reveals that, as in other institutions, there is a marked tendency for infection diseases to be underdiagnosed among workers due to the lack of adequate registration by professionals and competent authorities. This underdiagnosis leads to an incorrect classification (for example, as not data "ND" in the database analyzed), which limits adequate monitoring and the obtaining of accurate statistics, contributing to the increase in associated occupational morbidity and mortality.

Although current regulations establish clear definitions regarding risk assessment and workers' obligations, in practice, their application is insufficient. Higher education institution

faces specific challenges in complying with the implementation of prevention and control measures to mitigate the risk of transmission of infection disease at workplace. Therefore, the unification of information is a powerful tool, which will only be effective if used for decision-making and the development of occupational health policies, through the implementation of an ESSs.

As a proposal for implementation, we proposed an ESS focus in early detection of infection disease at the workplace, which emphasizes the importance of strengthening epidemiological surveillance of infectious diseases in the workplace to reduce the absenteeism.

One of the main challenges facing this project is the ethical balance between employee data privacy and the need to collect personal data for effective monitoring. Collecting sensitive information, such as health status and symptoms, raises concerns regarding informed consent, confidentiality, and safe use of data. Without adequate protection and anonymization protocols, there is a risk of generating mistrust among employees, which could limit participation and, consequently, the effectiveness of ESS.

Regarding the database analyzed, we decided to propose new variables to complete the data of workers with infectious diseases. These variables include sex (female or male), the sending and receiving of information obtained to the relevant entities, as well as determining whether the sick is for the first time, recurrent or due to a chronic infection disease.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the future implementation of this proposal represents a significant advance in strengthening the epidemiological surveillance of infection diseases at the workplace, providing an advanced technological tool that improves the response capacity to biological risks to prevent diseases of the worker population. This system not only optimizes the early detection of infectious diseases, but also fosters a culture of prevention in the workplace, helping to identify and mitigate risk factors more efficiently. However, the success of ESS will not depend solely on its technological implementation, but also on an ethical approach that guarantees the privacy and security of workers' data.

Furthermore, it will be essential that the system tailored to the specific needs of employees such as avoiding sickness from infection disease at work. Is the reason we propose to include new variables in the database will not only allow for more accurate monitoring of cases of occupational diseases but will also offer a comprehensive view of workers' health, allowing for more informed decisions and more effective occupational health policies. So we think an specific ESS has the potential to significantly improve worker safety and well-being, contributing to the creation of a healthier and more sustainable work environment in the long term.

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